

MAIN DIRECTIONS OF MEDICAL AND SOCIAL ASSISTANCE TO THE DISABLED

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Abstract. *In this article, the authors consider the main directions of medical and social assistance to the disabled in Uzbekistan.*

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Relevance. After gaining independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, along with great problems in the formation of a new independent state in industry, agriculture, culture, sports, education and other areas of the national economy, much attention is also paid to the health of the population, including the provision of comprehensive assistance to the disabled, i.e. the most disadvantaged segments of the population. In the republic there are people with disabilities of all age groups of the population, with disorders of the mental state, the musculoskeletal system and other organs, leading patients to permanent disability. For more than 20 years of the existence of the sovereign state of Uzbekistan, the state has adopted several hundred different policy documents, including Laws, Decrees, Resolutions of the President, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, orders and orders of the Ministers and health departments. Only on issues related to persons with disabilities, several dozen policy documents were adopted. These documents touched upon the issues of medical, professional and social rehabilitation of the disabled [2]. In order to combine efforts and coordinate the actions of public organizations of people with disabilities in the creation of an inclusive society, as well as the implementation of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, on February 21, 2018, on the initiative of public associations of people with disabilities, the Association of People with Disabilities of Uzbekistan was created and registered. To further improve the system of state social support for persons with disabilities, especially families caring for children in need of constant care, as well as to introduce new approaches to the implementation of modern social assistance mechanisms, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 17, 2022 No. UP- 74 On additional measures to support persons with disabilities and categories of the population in need of social protection”.

The purpose of this study was the study of the problem of rehabilitation of disabled people and the definition of the task of their medical, professional and social rehabilitation. Results and discussions. Analysis of documents adopted by the state and their implementation showed that the Republic of Uzbekistan organizes and promotes the formation and development of a system of medical, professional and social rehabilitation of people with disabilities, which is a set of measures aimed at restoring and compensating for impaired or lost body functions, self-care abilities, various types of professional activities, as well as allowing people with disabilities to lead a full-fledged lifestyle and ensuring their realization of their rights and potential opportunities. Today, according to the World Health Organization, about 1 billion people live in the world with various degrees of disability, 80% of whom are people from 18 to 64 years old. More than 780,000 people with disabilities live in Uzbekistan. Of these, disabled people of group

I make up 8.5%, group II - 71% and group III - 20.5%. Among persons with disabilities, children under 16 years of age account for 97,000 people. Therefore, social support for this segment of the population should be comprehensive. In this regard, legal guarantees of the rights of persons with disabilities were enshrined.[6]. To solve the problems of the individual rehabilitation program for the disabled, a set of measures is carried out that are carried out in accordance with the individual rehabilitation program, determined on the basis of medical and social expertise by state bodies authorized by the district, city Kengashes of people's deputies with the participation of representatives of public associations of disabled people. In an individual rehabilitation program recommended to a disabled person, specific volumes, types and terms of rehabilitation measures, as well as types of social assistance are determined. An individual rehabilitation program presented to disabled people is a document binding on the relevant state bodies, as well as enterprises, associations, institutions and organizations [4]. The rights of disabled people to participate in the life of society and protect their interests are enshrined in more than 80 laws and other regulatory legal acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at providing them with equal opportunities with other citizens in exercising civil, economic, political and other constitutional rights and freedoms, namely: in the laws "On Education", "On the Protection of the Health of Citizens", "On the Social Protection of the Disabled", "On the Employment of the Population", "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child", "On the State Pension Provision of Citizens", "On Labor Protection", "On physical culture and sports", the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, etc. Currently, the legal protection of the socio-economic rights of persons with disabilities in Uzbekistan has been strengthened: the Law "On social services for the elderly, disabled and other socially vulnerable categories of the population" dated December 26, 2016, which defined the concept of "social services", the list of persons who are entitled to receive social services and state bodies, organizations empowered to provide them, as well as the forms and types of provision of social support services, advisory services, services for home care, day (or) short-term care. The law determines the procedure for identifying persons in need of social services, organizing the implementation of individual programs of social services, subjects of state and public control in this area. On the basis of a critical study of the state of medical and social assistance to persons with disabilities, international standards in this area, on December 1, 2017, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically improve the system of state support for persons with disabilities" was adopted, which approved the Program of Comprehensive Measures for Further Improvement support systems for persons with disabilities and strengthening guarantees for the protection of their rights and freedoms[7].

The participation of not only the state, but also ordinary citizens in solving the pressing problems of persons with disabilities is very important. For these purposes, the Fund for the Support of Persons with Disabilities under the Ministry of Health is being created, since June 1, 2018, a unified electronic register of persons with disabilities has been introduced, including comprehensive information about them (personal data, amounts and types of cash payments, issued technical rehabilitation equipment, prosthetic and orthopedic products, etc.), which will ensure the organization of effective medical and rehabilitation work[1].

The Ministry of Justice has registered a non-governmental non-profit organization "Association of Disabled People of Uzbekistan". The main goals and objectives of the association are:

- Establishment and development of social partnership between members of the Association and state bodies in the field of social policy and development of civil society;

- Creation of equal opportunities for people with disabilities to exercise their rights, on an equal basis with other citizens;

- Full involvement and inclusion of persons with disabilities in all spheres of society:- Assistance in the implementation and implementation of the UN Convention "On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities";

- Establishment and development of cooperation with international organizations of disabled people.

To date, there are about 80 registered non-governmental non-profit organizations (NGOs) in Uzbekistan that deal with disability issues, but they are all fragmented. The main goal of the Association is to unite all NGOs on a voluntary basis to jointly solve the problems faced by people with disabilities. Also, one of the important tasks of the newly created association is the ratification of the UN Convention "On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities", as well as joining the International Organization of Persons with Disabilities[7]. Social assistance to the disabled is provided by the Kengashes of People's Deputies, their executive and administrative bodies, departments of social security, health care, public education, culture, physical culture and sports and other state bodies on the basis of the conclusions of medical and social expertise in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As part of the implementation of its own and State Programs, the Soglom Avlod Uchun Foundation is working on the development and implementation of medical, humanitarian, educational programs, projects to support gifted children and promote a healthy lifestyle, programs that cover vulnerable segments of the population, as well as children and youth.

All disabled people, regardless of age, gender, nationality, are provided with social assistance. There are several types of social assistance: social assistance to the disabled is provided in the form of cash payments (pensions, allowances, lump-sum payments), providing technical and other means, including cars, wheelchairs, prosthetic and orthopedic products, printed publications with a special font, sound-amplifying equipment and signaling devices, provision of services for medical, social and professional rehabilitation and consumer services, transport services [1]. In order to ensure the comprehensive and harmonious development of disabled children, educate them in social activity, interest in work, familiarization with science, technology, art and sports, public education bodies, other state bodies are obliged to ensure the availability of out-of-school education for disabled children, creating the necessary conditions for this. In 300 schools, programs for the development of inclusive education have been introduced, designed to teach children with disabilities. For persons with disabilities, an additional two percent quota for admission to higher educational institutions from the total number of admission of applicants is allocated[6]. For the preschool education of disabled children, the most favorable conditions are created for the upbringing and rehabilitation of such children of preschool age, whose health condition excludes the possibility of their stay in preschool institutions of a general type. institutions, including nursing homes. In order to organize general secondary, secondary specialized and higher education for disabled people, opportunities are being created for their education in all educational institutions, and, if necessary, in special educational institutions. Training sessions are also organized for disabled children undergoing treatment in inpatient medical and preventive or rehabilitation institutions. Disabled children permanently residing in stationary institutions, these institutions ensure the continuity of upbringing and education in limited connection with social and labor adaptation. The organization of upbringing and education of disabled children at home is carried out in the case when there is no opportunity to carry out the

upbringing and education of disabled people in general or special preschool institutions and educational institutions, and taking into account the wishes of parents, upbringing and education are carried out at home. At the same time, one of the parents or a person replacing him is provided with material support and benefits in the manner and on the conditions determined by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan[3]. Vocational training and advanced training of disabled people are provided in educational institutions, enterprises, associations and organizations (specialized or general), as well as enterprises and associations of public organizations of disabled people, together with social assistance institutions in accordance with an individual rehabilitation program. Material support for disabled people during the period of vocational training and advanced training is carried out at the expense of the state, in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Education, vocational training and advanced training of disabled people are carried out in various forms, including full-time and part-time forms, external studies, through training in special groups, classes and according to individual curricula, including home schooling. Having received certain labor skills, disabled people must use them correctly, and the state, public and other organizations should assist them in this. For disabled people to realize their right to work, the main thing is to ensure employment of disabled people, working conditions for disabled people and benefits for enterprises that employ disabled people. In order to ensure the employment of disabled people, state bodies, with the participation of trade unions and public organizations of disabled people, establish standards for booking at enterprises, associations, institutions and organizations of jobs for disabled people in the amount of at least three percent of the number of employees (at least 34 people). Disabled persons in need of post-care and assistance are provided by social assistance bodies with medical and household services at home or in stationary institutions. The state promotes the development of a network of stationary institutions of social assistance to disabled people in need of aftercare. If a worker or employee has received a disability due to the fault of an enterprise, association, institution, organization and needs outside care, then this enterprise, association, institution, organization is obliged at its own expense to support a home-based worker to care for the sick for the time of his loss of ability to work according to the conclusion of the health authorities and medical and labor expert commissions and compensate the victim for the material and moral damage caused to him [2]. The conditions for the stay of disabled people in a boarding school or other stationary institution of social assistance should ensure the possibility for disabled people to exercise their legitimate rights and interests and contribute to the maximum satisfaction of the needs of the individual. In the event that, as a result of rehabilitation measures, the need for further stay of a disabled person in a boarding school or other stationary institution of social assistance has disappeared, he must be provided with a comfortable living space by the local government body in accordance with the requirements of existing Laws. Disabled children staying in stationary institutions, who are orphans or deprived of parental care, upon reaching the age of majority, are provided by the Kengashes of People's Deputies out of turn with living space in accordance with an individual rehabilitation program, if it provides for the possibility of self-service and lead an independent lifestyle. Social services for the disabled, including the provision of food and other consumer goods, the provision of utilities and other services, are carried out on preferential terms determined by the Kengashes of People's Deputies with the participation of trade unions and public associations of the disabled, social assistance institutions. Kengashes of people's deputies at least once a year organize a survey of the social and living conditions of the disabled and take the necessary measures to improve them. The source of financing of social assistance to the disabled is, first of all, the state. Social

assistance is provided at the expense of the republican and local budgets, the off-budget Pension Fund, social protection funds for the disabled, as well as voluntary contributions from organizations, associations and citizens[5]. Enterprises, associations, institutions and organizations that finance activities related to the provision of social assistance to persons with disabilities are provided with tax benefits in the manner and on conditions determined by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1]. Conclusions. Thus, in Uzbekistan, the problems of medical adaptation and social rehabilitation of disabled people are dealt with by State bodies (Ministries of Health, Labor and Social Protection, Education, Culture and Sports), public organizations specially created in the republic - the Society of the Disabled, the International Non-Governmental Foundation "Soglom Avlod Uchun", " Children's Fund, Non-governmental non-profit organizations, Mahalla committees, as well as commissioners specially assigned at each enterprise for the employment of disabled people and the creation of the necessary conditions for them at the workplace.

REFERENCES

1. Abzalov, M. M. Asocial and economic features of the primary disability of the population of Tashkent / M. M. Abzalov, A. Abdufattaev // Economics of Health. Russia. - 2001. - No. 7-8 (56). - S. 10-60.
2. Asadov, D. A., Sharipova M. K. The importance of economic in terms of their disability since childhood and ways to optimize medical measures to reduce them / D.
3. A. Asadov, M. K. Sharipova // Pediatrics (Uzb.). - 2003. - Spec. Issue. - S. 6-4. Baleva, L. S. Rehabilitation assistance to children with disabilities and disabled since childhood / L. S. Baleva // Healthcare. Journal for the head and chief accountant. - 2002. - No. 10. - S. 66-69.
4. Dementieva, N. F. Social technologies, factors and mechanisms of socialization of disabled adolescents / N. F. Dementieva, O. Yu. Ivanova // Medico-social expertise and rehabilitation. - 2004. - No. 2. - S. 21-24.
5. Makhmudova N.M., Jalilova G.A., Mirdadaeva D.D., Tursunova H.N. The main directions of medical and social assistance to the disabled // Medicus. Russia -2017. No. 1 (13), 49 pages
6. Rasulev A. /How are persons with disabilities and pensioners protected in the country // <https://nuz.uz/obschestvo> Association of Disabled People of Uzbekistan, 21.02.2018 (<http://old.muslim.uz/index>.)